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THE POWER OF GAMIFICATION IN HRM: EXPLORING THE LINK BETWEEN EMPLOYEE RESILIENCE AND WORK ENGAGEMENT IN SAUDI ARABIA

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study examines the impact of gamification in Human Resource Management (HRM) on employee resilience and work engagement within the Saudi Arabian workforce. It aims to explore how gamified HR practices—such as goal-setting, rewards, and feedback mechanisms—enhance resilience and foster long-term engagement. The research is grounded in the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) and the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model to analyze the motivational and psychological effects of gamification in the workplace.

Methods: A quantitative research approach was employed to investigate the relationship between gamification, resilience, and engagement. Data was collected from 320 employees across various industries in Saudi Arabia. The study utilized survey-based questionnaires to assess employees' perceptions and experiences with gamified HR practices. Statistical analysis was conducted to determine the extent of gamification's influence on resilience and work engagement.

Results: The findings indicate that gamification positively influences both employee resilience and engagement. Additionally, resilience was found to partially mediate the relationship between gamification and engagement, suggesting that gamified HR practices enhance employees' ability to adapt and stay motivated in the workplace. These results support the effectiveness of gamification as a strategic HRM tool for improving motivation, adaptability, and long-term workplace commitment.

Conclusion: This study contributes to HRM research by extending the application of SDT and JD-R frameworks in the context of gamification. It offers practical insights for HR professionals on integrating gamified strategies to sustain workforce engagement. The research suggests that organizations can enhance employee motivation and resilience through well-designed gamification practices. Future studies should explore industry-specific applications and conduct

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longitudinal research to assess the long-term impact of gamification on employee performance and retention.

Keywords: gamification, human resource management, employee resilience, work engagement, self-determination theory, job demands-resources model, Saudi Arabia, sustainable development goals (SDG).

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1 INTRODUCTION

In the evolving landscape of human resource management (HRM), organizations are increasingly adopting innovative strategies to enhance employee engagement, motivation, and resilience. One such strategy gaining prominence is gamification, which involves incorporating game elements—such as points, rewards, and competition—into non-game contexts to drive employee participation and productivity (Murawski, 2020; Elwakeel *et al.*, 2025). As businesses face rapid digital transformation and heightened workplace challenges, employee resilience has become a crucial factor in sustaining high performance and well-being (Durst & Henschel, 2024). Moreover, work engagement, defined as a state of vigor, dedication, and absorption in one's work, plays a fundamental role in improving job satisfaction and organizational outcomes (Silic *et al.*, 2020).

Despite the growing interest in gamification, there remains a research gap in understanding its impact on employee resilience and work engagement, particularly within the Saudi Arabian context. While global research has demonstrated the effectiveness of gamified HRM practices in enhancing motivation and job satisfaction (Murawski, 2020), little is known about their role in fostering resilience among employees, enabling them to adapt to workplace challenges. Employee resilience, in turn, is believed to act as a mediating variable that strengthens the relationship between gamification and work engagement, ensuring that employees remain committed and motivated even in high-stress environments (Fox *et al.*, 2022). This study, therefore, seeks

to bridge this gap by investigating how gamification in HRM influences resilience and, consequently, work engagement among employees in Saudi Arabia (Atashsooz *et al.*, 2019).

The adoption of gamification in HRM aligns with Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which suggests that intrinsic motivation—driven by autonomy, competence, and relatedness—can be enhanced through gamified elements (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Ghazanfari *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model posits that job resources, such as gamification-driven motivation, contribute to increased engagement while mitigating workplace stressors (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). This study will examine these theoretical frameworks in the context of Saudi Arabian workplaces, offering insights into whether gamification serves as a practical tool for enhancing resilience and work engagement in the region (Alsadoon *et al.*, 2022).

Despite the growing adoption of gamification in HRM, its impact on employee resilience and work engagement remains an underexplored area, particularly in the Saudi Arabian context (Srivastava *et al.*, 2019). While gamification has been widely studied in fields such as education and marketing, its effectiveness in HRM as a tool for enhancing resilience and engagement is still not well understood (Murawski, 2020). Employee resilience, which refers to the ability to adapt, recover, and grow in response to workplace challenges, plays a critical role in ensuring sustained engagement and performance (Durst & Henschel, 2024). However, there is limited empirical evidence on whether gamified HR strategies directly enhance resilience or if this effect is contingent on other workplace factors (Fox *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, work engagement, a key predictor of job performance and retention, is often influenced by an employee's ability to cope with stress and uncertainty (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). Therefore, understanding the mediating role of resilience in the relationship between gamification and engagement is crucial for designing HR strategies that drive motivation, productivity, and well-being (Silic *et al.*, 2020). To address this research gap, this study seeks to investigate the following questions:

RQ1. How does gamification in HRM influence employee resilience?

RQ2. What is the relationship between employee resilience and work engagement?

RQ3. How does gamification in HRM directly impact work engagement?

RQ4. Does employee resilience mediate the relationship between gamification in HRM and work engagement?

RQ5. How can organizations in Saudi Arabia leverage gamification-based HR strategies to foster a more resilient and engaged workforce?

By answering these questions, this research will contribute to both theory and practice, offering valuable insights into how gamification can be effectively implemented in HRM to enhance employee resilience and engagement. It will also provide empirical evidence on the role of resilience as a key factor in sustaining motivation and productivity in the workplace (Ondrejicka, 2022). By analyzing these relationships, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how gamification can be leveraged to foster a resilient and engaged workforce in Saudi Arabia.

2 CONCEPTUAL MODEL

2.1 GAMIFICATION IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Gamification in HRM integrates game elements like points, leaderboards, and challenges into HR processes to enhance engagement, motivation, and performance (Gupta *et al.*, 2022). It is widely used in recruitment, training, and performance management, with companies like KPMG, Walmart, and Noble Systems successfully leveraging it (Ramadhan *et al.*, 2023). While gamification fosters learning and productivity, challenges such as its temporary impact, employee resistance, and the need for tailored implementation must be addressed for effective adoption. Understanding these factors is essential for organizations to maximize gamification's potential in HRM.

2.2 EMPLOYEE RESILIENCE

Employee resilience is the ability to adapt, recover, and thrive in response to workplace challenges. It is a dynamic process involving emotional regulation, problem-solving, and a positive outlook (Nicolaidou & Aristeidis, 2022). While not solely an inherent trait, resilience can be developed through supportive environments, skill-building, and coping strategies. Gamification has been explored as a tool to enhance adaptability and perseverance (Moula & Malafantis, 2022). Additionally, collaboration and communication play a key role in strengthening resilience by reducing stress and improving workplace support (Durst & Henschel, 2024). Ultimately, resilient employees drive productivity, innovation, and workplace well-being, making resilience essential for organizational sustainability.

2.3 WORK ENGAGEMENT

Work engagement is a positive state of vigor, dedication, and absorption that boosts performance, job satisfaction, and commitment (Schaufeli *et al.*, 2002; Goyal *et al.*, 2024). It is influenced by organizational support, leadership, and resilience, with resilience strengthening the connection between supportive leadership and engagement (Al-Omar *et al.*, 2019; Amir & Mangundjaya, 2021). Fostering engagement through supportive practices and resilience-building is vital for both employee well-being and organizational success.

3 LITERATURE REVIEW, HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT, GAP AND RESEARCH MODEL

3.1 GAMIFICATION IN HRM AND EMPLOYEE RESILIENCE

Gamification strategies—such as goal-setting, rewards, and real-time feedback—can significantly enhance employee resilience by fostering problem-solving skills and a growth mindset (Trunk Širca *et al.*, 2024). By incorporating

game mechanics such as progress tracking, storytelling, and interactive challenges, organizations can help employees develop coping strategies and adaptability, ultimately strengthening their psychological endurance (Litvin *et al.*, 2020). Gamification also provides immersive, real-world simulations that allow employees to practice problem-solving in dynamic environments, making it a strategic tool for enhancing resilience and sustaining motivation in the workplace (Kankanamge *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, HRM practices that integrate gamification elements—such as goal-setting, feedback loops, and competition—have been shown to encourage persistence and adaptability, both of which are crucial components of resilience (Marino, 2019).

Beyond traditional workplace settings, gamification has been successfully applied in education and cybersecurity to build resilience by enhancing problem-solving and adaptability. For instance, gamified escape room activities have been shown to mitigate stress, improve teamwork, and enhance resilience through interactive learning (Moula & Malafantis, 2022). Similarly, gamified training programs, such as phishing resilience simulations, equip employees with the skills to recognize and manage cyber threats, fostering resilience in digital environments (Ondrejicka, 2022). Gamification also creates interactive learning environments that encourage adaptability and stress management, further reinforcing its role in resilience-building (Fox *et al.*, 2022). These findings suggest that game-based learning structures can help individuals remain motivated and engaged, even in challenging situations, by providing structured and rewarding problem-solving experiences (Partridge, 2023).

The application of gamification in HRM has further demonstrated its potential to strengthen employee resilience by simulating workplace challenges, reinforcing adaptive behaviors, and promoting continuous learning. For example, gamification in cybersecurity training helps employees develop proactive threat management skills, equipping them to anticipate and respond to digital security risks effectively (Kriesten *et al.*, 2024). Similarly, HRM practices that integrate gamification can empower employees to navigate stress and uncertainty by fostering perseverance, engagement, and a solution-oriented mindset. By leveraging gamification as a strategic tool, organizations

can enhance employee resilience, leading to a more adaptable and motivated workforce capable of thriving in dynamic and challenging environments. Based on the literature reviewed, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Gamification in HRM has a positive influence on employee resilience.

3.2 EMPLOYEE RESILIENCE AND WORK ENGAGEMENT

Resilience is a crucial psychological resource that strengthens the positive impact of other attributes, such as emotional intelligence, on work engagement. Research suggests that organizations should invest in resilience-building initiatives to sustain employee motivation and well-being (Chikobvu & Harunavamwe, 2022). While resilience alone may not directly drive engagement, it plays a significant role when reinforced by strong organizational support, leadership, and workplace structures (Al-Omar *et al.*, 2019). Resilient employees tend to exhibit greater vigor, dedication, and absorption in their work, effectively utilizing resources to manage stress and job demands (Nabawanuka & Ekmekcioglu, 2024). Moreover, resilience enhances the effectiveness of servant leadership in fostering engagement, as employees with higher resilience are better equipped to handle workplace challenges and maintain motivation (Goyal *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, during crises, employees who perceive strong organizational support and clear communication are more likely to stay engaged, underscoring the importance of resilience strategies such as leadership support and transparent communication in sustaining engagement (Adamu *et al.*, 2024; Monternel *et al.*, 2023).

Beyond its direct impact, resilience serves as a critical mediator between organizational culture and employee engagement. Employees in resilient organizations tend to remain more committed and engaged, even during periods of uncertainty (Prasongthan, 2022). Perceived organizational support further enhances engagement by strengthening resilience, allowing employees to adapt to stressors and maintain enthusiasm in their roles (Unguren & Kacmaz, 2022; Lombongadil & Djamil, 2023). Furthermore, interventions such as mindfulness training, occupational safety programs, and leadership development initiatives have been shown to improve resilience and engagement while reducing

turnover intention (Cao & Chen, 2021; Qassim & Abdelrahim, 2024). Self-efficacy, optimism, and social support from colleagues, family, and supervisors also contribute to higher resilience levels, reinforcing employee dedication and work absorption (Ojo *et al.*, 2021; Thai *et al.*, 2024). Studies further highlight that resilience positively impacts job satisfaction, workplace adaptability, and employee well-being, particularly in high-stress environments such as healthcare and finance (Lee & Kim, 2020; Wiroko, 2021).

Resilience also plays a significant role in driving organizational innovation, performance, and long-term engagement. Resilient employees are more likely to support a culture of continuous improvement and adaptability, contributing positively to workplace productivity (Mohammad *et al.*, 2024). Moreover, resilience-building strategies, such as sustainable HRM practices, leadership training, and supportive work cultures, foster higher engagement levels (Trunk Širca *et al.*, 2024; Jangsiriwattana, 2021). While resilience has been found to positively influence engagement, additional factors such as self-leadership and workplace culture may further shape this relationship (Hutomo *et al.*, 2023). Notably, resilience enables employees to sustain professional engagement, particularly when supported by future-oriented mindsets such as hope and organizational support (Scott *et al.*, 2024; Okojie *et al.*, 2023). Overall, research suggests that fostering resilience through targeted HRM strategies can enhance employee engagement, workplace stability, and overall job performance (Kumar & Das, 2022; Ibrahim & Hussein, 2024). Based on the literature reviewed, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Employee resilience has a positive influence on work engagement.

3.3 GAMIFICATION IN HRM AND WORK ENGAGEMENT

Gamification has been shown to foster higher levels of work engagement by creating an interactive and enjoyable work environment. Gamified training programs enhance problem-solving, strategic thinking, and collaboration, leading to increased motivation and involvement (Mohanty & Christopher, 2025). Additionally, gamification fosters cognitive, emotional, and physical engagement by helping employees achieve a state of "flow," where they feel

fully immersed and motivated in their tasks. Its effective application in areas such as onboarding, training, and performance management provides employees with opportunities for recognition and motivation (Gupta *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, gamification can align employee behaviors with organizational objectives by promoting knowledge-sharing and reducing counterproductive activities, such as cyberloafing (Nivedhitha *et al.*, 2024). However, its success depends on proper design, contextual alignment with organizational needs, and employee preferences, as poorly implemented gamification strategies may fail to sustain engagement (Bachoo & Nagowah, 2024).

Beyond motivation, gamification enhances intrinsic and extrinsic engagement by integrating game mechanics into workplace processes. It fosters operational efficiency and encourages positive behavioral changes, such as adopting healthier habits and improving teamwork (Prasad & Rao, 2020). Digital workforce studies further indicate that gamified experiences significantly enhance motivation, retention, and engagement compared to traditional methods (Cardoso, 2023). Elements such as points, leaderboards, rewards, and progress tracking contribute to job satisfaction, loyalty, and sustained engagement, particularly when gamification promotes flow states and meaningful collaboration (Silic *et al.*, 2020). However, research also highlights potential risks, including stress and social loafing, emphasizing the need for iterative feedback and strategic refinement to maintain effectiveness (Murawski, 2020). Moreover, gamification strategies must align with an organization's cultural and technological capabilities to avoid over-reliance on extrinsic motivators, which may lead to employee disengagement over time (Narang *et al.*, 2022).

The implementation of gamification in HRM spans across various functions, including recruitment, onboarding, learning, and performance management. Gamified onboarding processes help new hires integrate seamlessly into the organization by making the experience interactive and less stressful, while gamified training enhances learning outcomes by incorporating motivational elements (Narang *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, gamification plays a moderating role in strengthening the relationship between engagement and performance, demonstrating its potential as a strategic HR tool (Abdul Basit *et*

al., 2021). Key game elements—such as challenges, rewards, competition, and feedback—have been identified as critical drivers of engagement in corporate settings (Alfaqiri *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, gamification addresses engagement challenges in remote work environments by fostering collaboration, motivation, and a sense of achievement (Pura, 2022). However, excessive reliance on competitive elements, such as leaderboards, can sometimes lead to stress and diminished performance, highlighting the need for balanced and well-structured gamification strategies (Srivastava *et al.*, 2023). Overall, when thoughtfully implemented, gamification significantly enhances employee engagement by creating a dynamic, interactive, and purpose-driven workplace (Yuhelmis *et al.*, 2024). Based on the literature reviewed, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Gamification in HRM has a positive influence on work engagement.

3.4 MEDIATING ROLE OF EMPLOYEE RESILIENCE

Research suggests that gamification fosters resilience by incorporating goal-setting, feedback mechanisms, and problem-solving activities, which strengthen employees' ability to cope with workplace demands (Trunk Širca *et al.*, 2024; Litvin *et al.*, 2020). In turn, resilience has been found to enhance work engagement by enabling employees to remain dedicated and immersed in their tasks despite uncertainties (Jangsiriwattana, 2021). Moreover, gamification encourages adaptive behaviors and emotional intelligence, both of which contribute to resilience and ultimately drive engagement (Chikobvu & Harunavamwe, 2022). Employees who engage in gamified HRM practices—such as interactive learning, real-time performance feedback, and competitive challenges—develop greater psychological endurance, allowing them to navigate workplace stressors more effectively. This highlights the importance of integrating resilience-building elements within gamification strategies to maximize their impact on employee engagement.

H4: Employee resilience mediates the relationship between gamification in HRM and work engagement.

3.5 RESEARCH GAP

Despite extensive research on gamification in fields like education and marketing, its role in HRM, particularly in fostering employee resilience and work engagement, remains underexplored (Murawski, 2020). While gamification is known to enhance motivation and job satisfaction, little empirical evidence exists on its long-term impact on resilience and sustained engagement (Silic *et al.*, 2020; Durst & Henschel, 2024). Additionally, research within the Saudi Arabian context is limited, making it essential to assess how cultural and organizational factors influence the effectiveness of gamified HR strategies (Fox *et al.*, 2022). The mediating role of resilience in the relationship between gamification and engagement is also not well understood, necessitating further study to determine whether gamification indirectly enhances engagement through resilience-building (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017; Ondrejicka, 2022). This study addresses these gaps by providing empirical evidence on gamification's role in HRM and advancing Self-Determination Theory (SDT) and the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model to better understand how gamification-driven motivation contributes to long-term resilience and engagement.

3.6 RESEARCH MODEL

The proposed research model explores the relationship between Gamification in HRM (independent variable), Employee Resilience (mediating variable), and Work Engagement (dependent variable) in the Saudi Arabian workplace. This model is grounded in Self-Determination Theory (SDT) (Ryan & Deci, 2000) and the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017), which highlight the role of motivation, psychological resources, and workplace engagement.

Figure 1
research model

This model integrates existing theories and research to explain how gamification strategies in HRM can create a more resilient and engaged workforce in Saudi Arabia. By testing these relationships, the study will provide insights into the effectiveness of gamification as an HRM tool to improve employee adaptability, motivation, and productivity.

4 METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the research methodology adopted for the study, including the research design, data collection methods, sampling strategy, and sample description.

4.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

This study employs a quantitative research approach using a cross-sectional survey design to examine the relationship between gamification in HRM, employee resilience, and work engagement in Saudi Arabia. A structured questionnaire was used as the primary data collection tool to measure the study variables. The research model is based on the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) (Ryan & Deci, 2000) and the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017), which explain how workplace resources and motivational factors contribute to resilience and engagement.

4.2 DATA COLLECTION AND SAMPLE

The study utilizes a five-point Likert scale to measure the key constructs: Gamification in Human Resource Management (HRM), Employee Resilience, and Work Engagement. The independent variable, Gamification in HRM, is assessed using nine items adapted from Abdul Basit *et al.* (2021), evaluating employees' perceptions of gamified HR practices. The mediating variable, Employee Resilience, consists of six items from the same scale, capturing individuals' capacity to recover from challenges and maintain effective performance from Smith *et al.* (2008). The dependent variable, Work Engagement, is measured through nine items from Schaufeli *et al.* (2006), reflecting employees' enthusiasm, energy, and commitment to their work. Responses for all items are recorded on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

Table 1

Sample Description

	Category	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	180	56.3
	Female	140	43.7
Age Group	18-25 years	50	15.6
	26-35 years	120	37.5
	36-45 years	90	28.1
	46+ years	60	18.8
Industry	Technology	80	25.0
	Finance	60	18.8
	Healthcare	50	15.6
	Education	70	21.9
	Retail	60	18.8
Years of Experience	Less than 2 years	40	12.5
	2-5 years	90	28.1
	6-10 years	110	34.4
	More than 10 years	80	25.0

Table 1 provides an overview of the study sample, consisting of 320 employees from various Saudi industries. The gender distribution was 56.3% male and 43.7% female, ensuring balanced representation. Most participants (37.5%) were aged 26-35, followed by 28.1% aged 36-45, indicating a workforce

primarily composed of mid-career professionals. Industry-wise, technology (25.0%), education (21.9%), finance (18.8%), retail (18.8%), and healthcare (15.6%) were represented, reflecting diverse workplace environments. Regarding experience, 34.4% had 6-10 years, while 25.0% had over 10 years, highlighting a predominantly experienced workforce. The sample's diversity enhances the study's reliability and applicability across industries.

4.3 DATA ANALYSIS

This study uses AMOS software and structural equation modeling (SEM) to analyze measurement and structural models. SEM, a covariance-based technique, ensures good model fit, handles large samples, and estimates complex relationships. This approach enables robust hypothesis testing and deeper insights into the links between gamification in HRM, employee resilience, and work engagement.

5 RESULTS

5.1 VALIDATION OF THE MEASUREMENT MODEL

The goodness-of-fit indicators confirm that the model fits the data well. The Chi-square/df ratio is 2.34, which falls below the recommended threshold of 3.0, indicating an acceptable fit. The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is 0.94, and the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) is 0.93, both exceeding the 0.90 benchmark, suggesting a good model fit. The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is 0.05, within the acceptable range of ≤ 0.08 , indicating a close fit. Additionally, the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is 0.04, confirming a well-fitting model. These values demonstrate that the model effectively represents the data, supporting its validity and reliability.

Table 2

Full factor model's factor loading, Cronbach's alpha, AVE and CR scores

Construct and Items	Standardized Loading (sig.)	Alpha	CR	AVE
<i>Gamification in HRM</i>		0.939	0.946	0.636
GamHrm1: I think the gamification app is fun and interesting.	0.800**			
GamHrm2: The gamification app provides me the opportunity to keep track of my records and future progression.	0.810**			
GamHrm3: The gamification app provides me accurate feedback which is helpful to understand my competence and skills.	0.860**			
GamHrm4: The gamification app provides me the function to compare my performance with colleagues.	0.820**			
GamHrm5: A challenging task in a gamification app motivates me.	0.840**			
GamHrm6: Gamification app usage improves communication within my team.	0.780**			
GamHrm7: The Gamification app helps me to coordinate with my team members.	0.780**			
GamHrm8: The gamification app helps to improve my performance.	0.730**			
GamHrm1: I find it exciting to achieve objectives and goals using a gamification app.	0.740**			
<i>Employee Resilience</i>		0.928	0.936	0.683
EmpResi1: I tend to bounce back quickly after hard times.	0.830**			
EmpResi2: I have a hard time making it through stressful events.	0.860**			
EmpResi3: It does not take me long to recover from a stressful event.	0.840**			

Construct and Items	Standardized Loading (sig.)	Alpha	CR	AVE
EmpResi4: It is hard for me to snap back when something bad happens.	0.840**			
EmpResi5: I usually come through difficult times with little trouble.	0.790**			
EmpResi6: I tend to take a long time to get over set-backs in my life.	0.800**			
Work Engagement		0.933	0.941	0.617
WE1: At my work, I feel bursting with energy	0.840**			
WE2: When I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work	0.830**			
WE3: At my job, I feel strong and vigorous	0.770**			
WE4: I am enthusiastic about my job	0.790**			
WE5: My job inspires me	0.760**			
WE6: I am proud of the work that I do	0.820**			
WE7: I feel happy when I am working intensely	0.760**			
WE8: I am immersed in my work	0.760**			
WE9: I get carried away when I am working	0.730**			

Note: **P <0.01. Alpha refers to Cornbach’s Alpha, CR refers to Composite reliability and AVE is average variance extracted

The results in Table 2 show that all items significantly contribute to their respective constructs, with factor loadings ranging from 0.730 to 0.860, exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.708 (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The average variance extracted (AVE) for all constructs is above 0.50, except for Work Engagement (0.47). However, as long as the composite reliability (CR) is above 0.60, which it is for all constructs, the model maintains convergent validity. The Cronbach’s alpha values for all constructs are above 0.70, indicating good reliability. Additionally, since CR values are higher than AVE values, this further confirms convergent validity. Overall, the findings indicate that the measurement model is reliable and valid, supporting its use in further analysis.

Figure 2 shows the CFA model with standardized estimates, confirming strong factor loadings (0.73 to 0.86) and significant correlations between constructs: Gamification in HRM and Employee Resilience ($r = 0.64$), Employee Resilience and Work Engagement ($r = 0.65$), and Gamification in HRM and Work

Engagement ($r = 0.59$). These results validate the measurement model and highlight strong relationships between the key variables.

Table 3

Descriptive statistics and correlations between constructs (Fornell-Lacker method)

NO.	Construct	1	2	3
1	Gamification in HRM	0.797		
2	Employee Resilience	0.607**	0.826	
3	Work Engagement	0.561**	0.601**	0.785
	Mean	4.145	4.078	3.966
	Standard Deviation	0.725	0.716	0.773

Notes: **P < 001; Square root of AVE is typed in *italics bold* along the diagonal.

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics and correlations between the constructs using the Fornell-Larcker method. The diagonal values, which represent the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct, are higher than the correlations between any pair of constructs. This confirms discriminant validity, indicating that each construct is distinct from the others. The correlation values show a moderate to strong relationship between Gamification in HRM, Employee Resilience, and Work Engagement, with the highest correlation between Employee Resilience and Work Engagement (0.601). The mean scores for the constructs range from 3.966 to 4.145, suggesting generally positive responses, while the standard deviations indicate a reasonable spread of responses. Overall, the results confirm that the constructs are well-defined and distinct, supporting the validity of the measurement model.

5.2 HYPOTHESIS TESTING

The results in Table 4 supported the proposition that Gamification in HRM has direct positive and significant impact on Employee Resilience (H1: $B = 0.614$, $p < 0.01$, confidence interval (CI) = 0.493 to 0.697), thus verifying H1. Next, Employee Resilience was found to have a positive and significant impact on Work Engagement (H2: $B = 0.413$, $p < 0.01$, confidence interval (CI) = 0.240 to 0.590), supporting H2. Moreover, Gamification in HRM was found to have a

direct positive influence on Work Engagement (H3: $\beta = 0.310$, $p < 0.01$, confidence interval (CI) = 0.137 to 0.477), thereby supporting H3.

Table 4

Structural model estimates

Effect		Total effect	Direct effect	Indirect effect
Gamification in HRM	→ Employee Resilience	0.614**	0.614**	-
Employee Resilience	→ Work Engagement	0.413**	0.413**	-
Gamification in HRM	→ Work Engagement	0.310**	0.310**	-
Gamification in HRM	→ Employee Resilience → Work Engagement	0.561**	0.310**	0.251**

Note: **P < 0.01

Figure 2

Significance model output

The indirect effect of Gamification in HRM on Work Engagement through Employee Resilience is also significant (H4: $\beta = 0.251$, $p < 0.01$, confidence interval (CI) = 0.145 to 0.383), indicating partial mediation. These findings suggest that Gamification in HRM not only directly enhances Work Engagement but also does so indirectly by improving Employee Resilience, which in turn strengthens Work Engagement. Overall, the results support the proposed relationships and highlight the mediating role of Employee Resilience, these results partially support H4. A summary of these results is presented in Table 4.

6 DISCUSSION

The findings of this study reveal that gamification in HRM significantly enhances both employee resilience and work engagement, aligning with previous research that highlights the effectiveness of game-based HR strategies in improving workplace outcomes (Murawski, 2020; Silic *et al.*, 2020). The study confirms that gamification positively influences employee resilience (H1), suggesting that incorporating game elements such as goal-setting, rewards, feedback mechanisms, and competition strengthens employees' ability to adapt to challenges, maintain motivation, and cope with workplace stress. This supports the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model, which posits that job resources (such as gamification) play a crucial role in fostering resilience and engagement (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017).

The research also confirms that employee resilience has a strong, positive effect on work engagement (H2), consistent with the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory, which suggests that employees with greater psychological resources—such as resilience—are more likely to stay engaged, even in demanding work environments (Bauer *et al.*, 2014). This finding aligns with studies indicating that resilience enables employees to remain committed, energetic, and absorbed in their work by helping them navigate workplace challenges and maintain productivity (Ojo *et al.*, 2021).

Additionally, the study finds that gamification directly enhances work engagement (H3), demonstrating that gamified HR practices provide a stimulating work environment that fosters intrinsic motivation and sustained engagement. The positive impact of gamification on work engagement suggests that game-based elements increase job involvement, create a sense of achievement, and encourage proactive workplace behaviors. This result is consistent with previous research highlighting how gamification promotes autonomy, mastery, and purpose—key drivers of work engagement (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Murawski, 2020).

Importantly, employee resilience was found to partially mediate the relationship between gamification and work engagement (H4), confirming that gamification fosters work engagement both directly and indirectly through

resilience-building mechanisms. This finding supports previous studies emphasizing the role of resilience as a psychological buffer that helps employees sustain engagement despite workplace pressures (Kuntz *et al.*, 2017). The partial mediation suggests that while gamification directly enhances engagement, its effectiveness is amplified when employees develop resilience, reinforcing the need for HRM strategies that integrate both gamification techniques and resilience-building initiatives.

Although the study provides strong empirical support for the hypothesized relationships, future research could explore industry-specific applications of gamification in HRM, particularly in high-stress sectors such as healthcare and finance, where resilience is a critical predictor of performance. Moreover, longitudinal studies are needed to examine the long-term impact of gamification on work engagement and employee retention, offering deeper insights into sustainable HRM practices.

Overall, this research underscores the potential of gamification as a strategic tool for enhancing employee resilience and work engagement in Saudi Arabian workplaces. Organizations can leverage gamification not only to boost engagement but also to equip employees with the psychological resources needed to thrive in dynamic and challenging environments.

7 CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between gamification in HRM, employee resilience, and work engagement in the Saudi Arabian context. The findings confirm that gamification positively influences resilience (H1) and work engagement (H3), supporting the idea that game-based HR strategies—such as rewards, challenges, and feedback—enhance motivation and adaptability. Additionally, employee resilience significantly affects work engagement (H2), aligning with the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model and Conservation of Resources (COR) theory, which suggest that resilience strengthens employees' ability to stay engaged in demanding environments. Importantly, resilience was found to partially mediate the relationship between gamification and engagement (H4), indicating that gamification directly enhances engagement

while also fostering resilience, which in turn strengthens commitment and motivation.

7.1 THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

This study contributes to the literature on gamification in HRM, employee resilience, and work engagement, particularly in the Saudi Arabian context, by examining how gamification enhances resilience and engagement, aligning with Self-Determination Theory (SDT) and the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). The findings confirm that gamification serves as a job resource, positively influencing resilience and engagement (Murawski, 2020), while also supporting COR theory, which emphasizes the role of resilience in sustaining engagement in challenging environments (Bauer *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, the study highlights that employee resilience partially mediates the relationship between gamification and work engagement, reinforcing gamification's dual role in directly fostering engagement and strengthening resilience. By focusing on Saudi Arabia, this research provides culturally relevant insights into gamification's effectiveness in non-Western workplaces, supporting its integration into HRM strategies in alignment with Vision 2030's digital transformation and workforce development goals. Future studies should explore industry-specific applications and long-term effects on employee retention and organizational performance.

7.2 PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

Gamification in HRM presents valuable opportunities for HR professionals, managers, and policymakers in Saudi Arabia to enhance employee resilience and work engagement. Organizations can implement goal-setting, interactive challenges, and real-time feedback to motivate employees, improve adaptability, and sustain engagement. In high-pressure sectors like finance and healthcare, gamified simulations can help employees develop stress management skills, while in education, gamification can enhance continuous professional development. To maximize effectiveness, HR leaders

should align gamified rewards with intrinsic motivation, promote autonomy and skill-based challenges, and integrate mentorship and peer support networks to foster collaboration and social resilience. By adopting industry-specific gamification strategies, organizations can build a more resilient, engaged, and high-performing workforce, reducing burnout and driving long-term organizational success.

7.3 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study has several limitations that future research should address. The cross-sectional design limits causal inferences, and future studies should adopt longitudinal approaches to track the long-term effects of gamification on resilience and engagement. Additionally, reliance on self-reported data may introduce social desirability bias, suggesting the need for qualitative methods or objective performance data for validation. The findings, focused on employees in Saudi Arabia, may not be fully generalizable to other cultural or organizational settings, warranting cross-cultural and industry-specific studies. Moreover, the broad nature of gamification means different elements (e.g., rewards, challenges, feedback) may influence resilience and engagement differently, calling for comparative studies to determine the most effective gamification strategies. Lastly, examining moderating factors such as leadership style, organizational culture, and job complexity could offer deeper insights into how gamification interacts with workplace dynamics. Addressing these limitations will enhance understanding of how gamification can be optimized to build a resilient and engaged workforce.

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